

Comparative evaluation of the performance and costs of hydrogen and compressed air energy storage in salt caverns

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Abstract

Due to their excellent potential for holding compressed gases, salt caverns are widely considered to be a key resource in the UK for long duration energy storage. Candidate gases primarily include hydrogen and compressed air for energy storage. The properties (*i.e.* operation, energy storage, efficiency, *etc.*) of these systems differ significantly, but so far, comparative analysis of these two key options has been limited. Therefore, in this work we perform a comparative analysis of these two long-duration energy storage technologies at two cavern depths, a shallow cavern (circa 500m depth) and a deep cavern (circa 1500m depth). At each depth, we undertake a high-level design of the system based on the operational pressure, as determined by the lithostatic pressure and cavern structural requirements. We find that the energy density of hydrogen systems is considerably higher, however the ACAES systems have higher efficiency at both depths (~64%). Conversely, the hydrogen storage efficiency is lower in the deeper system due to the extra compression work required (~40% compared with ~38% for the shallow and deep systems respectively). For both systems, the capital expense per unit of stored energy is considerably lower for the deeper systems. Our analysis highlights that each of these systems offers considerably different storage capabilities, and therefore the best option is likely to be highly dependent on the energy system that sits above the surface.

Keywords

Salt caverns, underground long duration energy storage, compressed air energy storage, hydrogen storage

1 Introduction

Among the technologies proposed for large-scale Long-duration energy storage (LDES), underground storage of compressed gases within salt caverns has attracted considerable interest owing to the large storage capacities that can be achieved and the maturity of the underlying geological storage technology. In particular, salt caverns have been identified as a potentially strategic asset for both hydrogen (H₂) energy storage and compressed air energy storage (CAES), two technologies capable of delivering

gigawatt to terawatt-hours over long discharge durations. These caverns are typically formed by solution mining halite deposits and provide large, gas-tight storage volumes with high deliverability, making them well suited to large-scale energy storage applications involving hydrogen, compressed air, and natural gas.

The United Kingdom possesses a substantial salt resource distributed across several major onshore sedimentary basins, principally the Cheshire, East Yorkshire and Wessex basins [9]. Recent studies have suggested that the UK salt resource could provide extremely large quantities of underground gas storage. Williams *et al.* [9] estimated an upper technical potential of approximately 2150 TWh of hydrogen storage, whilst more conservative assessments have proposed significantly lower but still substantial values. For example, Garvey *et al.* [4] estimated that the East Coast Cluster alone could accommodate approximately 48 TWh of hydrogen storage. These estimates are comparable to, or exceed, the storage requirements identified in recent assessments of future UK energy systems. The Royal Society report on LDES has suggested that between 60 and 100 TWh of LDES may be required to support a net-zero electricity system [7].

Despite the recognised strategic importance of salt caverns, most studies have focused on either hydrogen storage or CAES in isolation. Relatively few investigations have undertaken a direct comparison of the two technologies using a consistent modelling framework. Such comparisons are important because the performance and economics of both technologies are strongly influenced by the geological characteristics of the storage resource.

One of the most important geological parameters is cavern depth. The depth of a salt cavern determines the lithostatic pressure acting on the surrounding formation and therefore constrains the allowable operating pressure range of the store. A commonly adopted design guideline is that cavern operating pressures should lie between approximately 25–80% of the lithostatic pressure in order to maintain cavern stability and avoid excessive deformation of the surrounding salt formation [4]. Consequently, deeper caverns permit substantially higher storage pressures than shallower caverns. Since both CAES and hydrogen storage rely on compressed gas storage, variations in cavern depth directly affect energy density, storage capacity, compressor and turbine requirements, and ultimately system economics. The objective of this study is therefore to undertake a comparative technical assessment of hydrogen and CAES systems deployed within salt caverns at different depths.

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2 Methodology

2.1 System configurations

Figure 1: Comparison of adiabatic compressed air energy storage (ACAES) and hydrogen storage pathways using underground salt caverns.

The two cavern depths were selected to represent the range of operating pressures encountered within UK salt formations – approximately 500 m in the Cheshire basin and 1500 m in East Yorkshire. At each depth, both ACAES and hydrogen storage are modelled, giving four systems in total:

- (1) ACAES at 500 m depth;
- (2) Hydrogen storage at 500 m depth;
- (3) ACAES at 1500 m depth;
- (4) Hydrogen storage at 1500 m depth.

Both systems are assessed on an electrical-to-electrical basis, as illustrated in Figure 1, though additional value pathways (waste heat utilisation, hydrogen for heating or fuel cells) are not considered here. A cavern volume of 500,000 m³ is assumed throughout. A quasi-steady thermodynamic model is developed for each system, in which charging and discharging are represented as sequences of finite mass increments entering or leaving the cavern, allowing pressure, temperature and stored energy to evolve throughout each cycle.

2.2 ACAES system model

An ACAES system is considered, since this is the furthest developed of the next-generation CAES technologies [2]. During charging, ambient air is compressed through a series of inter-cooling stages before entering the cavern. Thermal energy removed during compression is stored within dedicated thermal energy storage (TES) units and subsequently recovered during discharge to reheat the air prior to expansion. The ACAES system comprises a multi-stage compressor train with intercooling, pressurised-water TES, a salt cavern air store, and a multi-stage expansion train with reheating. Separate TES units are assumed for each compression stage, with each store thermally coupled to the corresponding expansion stage during discharge.

2.2.1 Charging process. The charging process is modelled by passing a small mass increment of air, Δm , through the compressor stages and into the cavern. Assuming polytropic compression, the outlet temperature of a compression stage is

$$T_2 = T_1 \left(\frac{p_2}{p_1} \right)^{\frac{k_c - 1}{k_c}} \quad (1)$$

where p_1 and p_2 are the inlet and outlet pressures respectively, and k_c is the effective polytropic exponent determined from the design-point isentropic compressor efficiency η_c , as shown in Equation 2.

$$k_c = \frac{\eta_c \gamma}{\eta_c \gamma - \gamma + 1} \quad (2)$$

The work input associated with the compression of a mass increment is

$$W_c = \Delta m c_p (T_2 - T_1) \quad (3)$$

where c_p is the specific heat capacity of air.

Heat generated during compression is removed using balanced heat exchangers (HX). Assuming equal heat-capacity rates for the air and coolant streams, the coolant outlet temperature is calculated from

$$T_{w,out} = T_{w,in} + \varepsilon (T_{a,in} - T_{w,in}) \quad (4)$$

where ε is the HX effectiveness, taken as 0.85, and the subscripts a and w denote air and water respectively.

Pressurised water at 5 bar is employed as the thermal storage medium. To avoid boiling within the thermal storage system, the water temperature is constrained to remain below 150°C. This requirement determines the number of compression stages required for each cavern depth, resulting in five stages for the 500 m cavern and six stages for the 1500 m cavern.

The compression train is designed with equal on-design pressure ratios. As cavern pressure increases during charging, stages whose design outlet pressure exceeds the cavern pressure are bypassed, causing the final active stage to operate with a variable pressure ratio. The TES units are assumed to be perfectly mixed and the charging power is fixed at 250 MW.

2.2.2 Discharging process. During discharging in the model, air is withdrawn from the cavern in discrete mass increments and passed through a multi-stage expansion train. Prior to each turbine stage, the compressed air is reheated using the corresponding TES unit. Assuming balanced HX units with the same HX effectiveness of $\varepsilon = 0.85$, the turbine inlet temperature is given by

$$T_{t,in} = T_{a,in} + \varepsilon (T_{TES} - T_{a,in}) \quad (5)$$

where T_{TES} is the temperature of the water entering the HEX from the associated thermal store and $T_{a,in}$ is the temperature of the air entering the HX from either the air store or the outlet of the previous stage expander. The turbine outlet temperature is calculated assuming polytropic expansion,

$$T_{out} = T_{in} \left(\frac{p_{out}}{p_{in}} \right)^{\frac{k_e - 1}{k_e}} \quad (6)$$

where k_e is the effective expansion exponent. Like the compressor, this is determined from the expander on-design isentropic efficiency, η_t , as shown in Equation 7.

Table 1: ACAES system configuration parameters.

Parameter	500 m	1500 m
V_c [m ³]	500,000	500,000
P_{start} [MPa]	4.08	11.76
P_{min} [MPa]	4.0	11.0
P_{max} [MPa]	7.0	28.0
n_c [-]	5	6
n_e [-]	5	6
t_{idle} [h]	12	50
P_c [MW]	250	250
P_d [MW]	250	250

Table 2: Thermophysical and component parameters used in the ACAES model.

Parameter	Value
T_{amb} [K]	293
R [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	287
c_p [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	1005
c_v [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	718
γ [-]	1.40
η_c [-]	0.85
η_e [-]	0.85
ϵ_{HX} [-]	0.85
c_w [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	4182
ρ_w [kg m ⁻³]	1000
$T_{\text{TES,max}}$ [K]	423
k_{air} [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	0.03
μ_{air} [Pa s]	1.85×10^{-5}

$$k_e = \frac{\gamma}{\gamma - \eta_t \gamma + \eta_t} \quad (7)$$

The work recovered from each expansion stage is

$$W_t = \Delta m C_p (T_{\text{in}} - T_{\text{out}}). \quad (8)$$

The expansion train follows the same stage-bypassing logic as the compression train, with the highest-pressure active stage operating at a variable pressure ratio determined by the instantaneous cavern pressure.

The discharge power is fixed at 250 MW. Table 1 summarises the main parameters used in the two ACAES systems. In Table 1, V_c is the cavern volume, P_{start} is the initial cavern pressure, P_{min} and P_{max} are the minimum and maximum allowable cavern pressures, n_c and n_e are the numbers of compression and expansion stages, t_{idle} is the mid-cycle idle period and P_c and P_d are the charging and discharging powers, respectively.

The cavern is modelled as a lumped control volume with uniform pressure and temperature. Following the addition or removal of each mass increment of air, the cavern mass and internal energy are updated to determine the new cavern state.

The cavern pressure is calculated from the ideal gas equation,

$$p_c = \frac{m_c R T_c}{V_c} \quad (9)$$

where m_c is the mass of air within the cavern, T_c is the cavern temperature, V_c is the cavern volume and R is the specific gas constant of air.

For charging, a mass increment Δm enters the cavern at temperature T_{in} . Neglecting heat transfer, conservation of energy gives the adiabatic cavern temperature

$$T_{c,\text{ad}} = \frac{\Delta m c_p T_{\text{in}} + m_c c_v T_c}{c_v (m_c + \Delta m)} \quad (10)$$

where c_p and c_v are the specific heat capacities of air at constant pressure and constant volume respectively. Similarly, during discharge, a mass increment Δm is removed from the cavern. Applying conservation of energy yields

$$T_{c,\text{ad}} = \frac{m_c c_v T_c - \Delta m c_p T_c}{c_v (m_c - \Delta m)} \quad (11)$$

which represents the adiabatic cooling of the cavern associated with mass withdrawal. The adiabatic temperature is subsequently corrected to account for heat exchange between the cavern air and the surrounding salt formation. The heat transferred between the cavern air and wall during a timestep is

$$\dot{Q}_{c,w} = h A_c (T_{c,\text{ad}} - T_w) \quad (12)$$

where h is the convective heat transfer coefficient, A_c is the cavern wall area and T_w is the cavern wall temperature. The convective heat transfer coefficient between the cavern air and wall is determined using a natural convection correlation based on the Rayleigh and Nusselt numbers for an equivalent spherical cavern geometry.

Table 3: Key parameters used in the cavern thermal model.

Parameter	Value
Depth (shallow cavern)	500 m
Depth (deep cavern)	1500 m
Salt thermal conductivity, k_{salt}	$5.5 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Salt density, ρ_{salt}	2160 kg m^{-3}
Salt heat capacity, $c_{p,\text{salt}}$	$880 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Geothermal temperature, T_{geo}	$T_{\text{amb}} + 32 \left(\frac{\text{Depth}}{1000} \right)$

2.3 Cavern wall temperature model

We employ a semi-analytical cavern thermal model in which heat exchange occurs between the compressed air and the surrounding salt formation throughout charging, idle and discharging periods. The instantaneous heat transfer rate between the cavern air and wall is given by

$$\dot{Q}_{c,w} = h A_c (T_c - T_w) \quad (13)$$

where h is the convective heat transfer coefficient, A_c is the cavern wall area, T_c is the cavern air temperature and T_w is the wall temperature. To determine the wall temperature, the salt formation is modelled as a semi-infinite solid. The cavern wall corresponds to the surface $x = 0$, whilst the salt temperature far from the cavern remains at the undisturbed geothermal temperature, T_{geo} . Defining

$$\theta(x, t) = T(x, t) - T_{\text{geo}}, \quad (14)$$

the temperature field within the salt satisfies the one-dimensional transient heat conduction equation

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \alpha_s \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x^2} \quad (15)$$

where $\alpha_s = k_s / (\rho_s c_s)$ is the thermal diffusivity of the salt, k_s is the thermal conductivity, ρ_s is the density and c_s is the specific heat capacity. At the cavern wall, conservation of energy requires

that the conductive heat flux into the salt equals the heat flux exchanged with the cavern air, giving

$$-k_s \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=0} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{cw}(t)}{A_c} \quad (16)$$

Assuming the salt formation behaves as a semi-infinite medium, the resulting wall temperature can be obtained analytically yielding

$$T_w(t) = T_{geo} + \frac{\sqrt{\alpha_s}}{k_s \sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^t \frac{\dot{Q}_{cw}(\tau)}{\sqrt{t-\tau}} d\tau \quad (17)$$

where τ is a dummy time variable representing a previous instant in the thermal history of the cavern wall.

Within the numerical implementation, the wall heat flux is assumed constant during each timestep. The heat flux history is therefore represented as a sequence of piecewise-constant intervals, allowing Equation 17 to be evaluated analytically over each timestep. The resulting discrete expression is

$$T_w(t) = T_{geo} + \frac{2\sqrt{\alpha_s}}{k_s \sqrt{\pi}} \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\dot{Q}_{cwj}}{A_c} [\sqrt{t-t_{j-1}} - \sqrt{t-t_j}] \quad (18)$$

where \dot{q}'_j is the wall heat flux during timestep j , and t_{j-1} and t_j denote the beginning and end of the timestep respectively.

The main cavern parameters are summarised in Table 3.

2.4 Hydrogen energy storage model

The hydrogen energy storage system consists of an electrolyser, a multi-stage compression train, a salt cavern hydrogen store and a hydrogen-fuelled combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT). As with the ACAES system, a quasi-steady model is employed.

2.4.1 Hydrogen production and power generation. Hydrogen is produced by the electrolyser at a rate determined by

$$\dot{m}_{H_2} = \frac{\eta_{el} P_C}{HHV_{H_2}} \quad (19)$$

where P_C is the charging power, η_{el} is the electrolyser efficiency and HHV_{H_2} is the higher heating value of hydrogen.

During discharge, electrical energy is generated using a hydrogen-fired combined cycle gas turbine with efficiency η_{CCGT} . The electrical energy recovered from a hydrogen mass increment Δm is therefore

$$E_{out} = \eta_{CCGT} \Delta m HHV_{H_2}. \quad (20)$$

2.4.2 Hydrogen compression. The electrolyser outlet pressure is assumed to be 30 bar. For cavern pressures exceeding the electrolyser delivery pressure, hydrogen is compressed using a multi-stage compression train with intercooling between stages. The specific compressor work is calculated assuming polytropic compression. The total compressor power requirement is added to the electrical energy required by the electrolyser such that

$$P_{charge} = P_{electrolyser} + P_{compressor}. \quad (21)$$

2.4.3 Hydrogen cavern model. The hydrogen cavern is modelled as a lumped control volume with uniform pressure and temperature. As hydrogen is added or removed, the cavern mass and internal energy are updated using the same control-volume formulation employed for the ACAES model. The adiabatic cavern

Table 4: Hydrogen system configuration parameters.

Parameter	Value
P_c [MW]	250
P_d [MW]	250
P_{elec} [MPa]	3.0
P_{margin} [MPa]	2.0
n_c [-]	3
T_{ic} [K]	303.15
T_{inj} [K]	303.15
η_{elec} [-]	0.74
η_{CCGT} [-]	0.55
η_c [-]	0.75
t_{idle} [h]	48 / 500
t_{rec} [h]	48 / 500

Table 5: Hydrogen thermophysical properties.

Parameter	Value
HHV_{H_2} [MJ kg ⁻¹]	142
c_p [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	14209
c_v [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	10085
R [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	4124
γ [-]	1.409
k_{H_2} [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	0.180
μ_{ref} [Pa s]	8.76×10^{-6}
T_0 [K]	273.15
S [K]	72

temperature is calculated using Equation 10 or 11 and then updated to account for heat transfer. Heat transfer between the cavern gas and surrounding salt formation is calculated using the natural-convection assuming hydrogen thermophysical properties. The cavern pressure is calculated using

$$p_c = \frac{Z m_c R T_c}{V_c} \quad (22)$$

where Z is the hydrogen compressibility factor, R is the hydrogen gas constant and V_c is the cavern volume. The compressibility factor is evaluated using the pressure-virial correlation proposed by Lemmon *et al.* [6], enabling non-ideal hydrogen behaviour to be captured at the storage pressures considered in this study.

2.5 Capital cost model

The capital cost of each storage system was estimated by summing the costs of the major equipment components using the literature correlations summarised in Table 6, where Π is the stage pressure ratio, η is the isentropic efficiency, P is the component rated power, \dot{m} is the working-fluid mass flow rate, T_{in} is the turbine inlet temperature, A is the heat transfer area, and V denotes storage volume. For the ACAES system, compressor and turbine costs were estimated using the correlations proposed by Baniamerian *et al.* [1], which account for the influence of operating pressure on turbomachinery cost. HX costs were estimated as a function of heat transfer area, while thermal energy storage costs were based on sensible heat storage correlations and scaled with storage volume.

For the hydrogen system, electrolyser and inverter costs were assumed to scale linearly with rated electrical power. Hydrogen-fired CCGT costs were estimated from conventional natural gas combined cycle plant costs multiplied by a factor of three to account for hydrogen-specific modifications. Hydrogen compression costs were estimated using correlations developed for high-pressure hydrogen compressors, while salt cavern costs were

Table 6: Component cost correlations used in the techno-economic assessment.

Component	Correlation	Ref.
ACAES compressor	$C_{\text{comp}} = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\Pi}}\right)^{1.33} \left[\frac{300}{1-\eta} P_{\text{MW}}^{0.68}\right] 1000$	[1]
ACAES turbine	$C_{\text{turb}} = (\sqrt{\Pi})^{0.8} \left[\frac{1800}{1-\eta} \dot{m} \ln\left(\frac{P_{\text{in}}}{P_{\text{out}}}\right) (1 + e^{0.036T_{\text{in}} - 65.66})\right]$	[1]
Heat exchanger	$C_{\text{HX}} = (1.3 + 1.88) 65 \left(\frac{A}{1000}\right)$	[8]
Thermal energy storage	$C_{\text{TES}} = 563 + 0.22V_{\text{TES}}$	[8]
Electrolyser	$C_{\text{Elec}} = 1728P_{\text{kW}}$	[5]
Inverter	$C_{\text{Inv}} = 200P_{\text{kW}}$	[10]
Hydrogen compressor	$C_{\text{H}_2\text{Comp}} = 40035P_{\text{kW}}^{0.68}$	[10]
Hydrogen-fired CCGT	$C_{\text{CCGT}} = 1000P_{\text{kW}}$	[3]
Salt cavern	$C_{\text{cav}} = 23V_{\text{cav}}$	[10]

Table 7: Performance and economic results for the shallow (500 m) cavern systems.

Metric	ACAES	H ₂
Charge time [h]	6.3	65.3
Discharge time [h]	4.1	26.0
Round-trip efficiency [%]	64.3	39.8
Total CAPEX [M\$]	186.0	744.0
Cost per recovered kWh [\$ kWh ⁻¹]	182.3	114.5

assumed to scale linearly with cavern volume and were applied equally to both storage technologies.

3 Results and discussion

All systems were assigned a charging power of 250 MW and a discharging power of 250 MW. Tables 7 and 8 summarise the key performance and economic metrics for the shallow and deep cavern systems, respectively.

For the shallow cavern, ACAES exhibits substantially shorter charging and discharging durations than hydrogen storage owing to its lower energy storage capacity. The ACAES system achieves a round-trip efficiency of 64.3%, considerably higher than the 39.8% obtained for the hydrogen system. The lower hydrogen efficiency is primarily attributable to losses associated with electrolysis and the hydrogen-fired CCGT.

Both systems exhibit significant thermal interaction with the surrounding salt formation. Compression raises cavern gas temperatures, while heat transfer to the cavern walls during charging and idle periods produces a thermal memory effect that influences subsequent discharge behaviour. As shown in Figure 2, the cavern wall temperature responds more slowly than the gas temperature due to the thermal inertia of the surrounding salt formation.

Although the hydrogen system exhibits a considerably higher total CAPEX, its larger storage capacity results in a lower cost per recovered kilowatt-hour. These values represent capital cost normalised by recoverable electrical energy and do not constitute an LCOS metric.

Table 8: Performance and economic results for the deep (1500 m) cavern systems.

Metric	ACAES	H ₂
Charge time [h]	47.7	958
Discharge time [h]	30.4	365
Round-trip efficiency [%]	63.8	38.1
Total CAPEX [M\$]	339.0	757.5
Cost per recovered kWh [\$ kWh ⁻¹]	44.6	8.3

The deeper cavern provides substantially greater storage capacity owing to the increased operating pressure range. Consequently, charging and discharging durations increase considerably for both storage technologies. For ACAES, the charging duration increases from approximately 6 hours to almost 48 hours, whilst the discharge duration increases from approximately 4 hours to over 30 hours.

The thermal response of the deep ACAES cavern differs from that of the shallow system due to the higher geothermal temperature associated with the greater overburden depth. The round-trip efficiency decreases slightly from 64.3% to 63.8% due to the fixed maximum TES temperature constraint, which results in higher losses at higher pressure. The hydrogen system experiences smaller temperature variations during charging due to the longer charging duration, resulting in only minor changes in cavern wall temperature. However, due to the larger losses, the temperature drop during discharge is larger than during charge. A notable result is the substantial reduction in cost per recovered kilowatt-hour for both technologies at greater depth. The deeper cavern permits significantly more energy to be stored within the same cavern volume whilst only modestly increasing equipment costs. This effect is particularly pronounced for hydrogen storage, where the cost per recovered kilowatt-hour decreases from \$114.5 kWh⁻¹ to \$8.3 kWh⁻¹. These results highlight the strong influence of cavern pressure on the economic viability of underground gas storage systems.

3.1 Limitations and future work

The results presented in this study should be interpreted in the context of several modelling assumptions. The HX sizing methodology is intended to provide an approximate indication of component scale and cost rather than a detailed design. The HX models neglect pressure losses and assume a fixed effectiveness throughout operation. Off-design turbomachinery operation has not been considered rigorously. Furthermore, the heat transfer coefficients and required heat transfer areas are likely to vary throughout the operating cycle as flow rates and temperature differences change. In addition, several potentially significant cost elements have been excluded from the economic assessment, including cushion gas requirements, brine disposal, cavern development costs and site-specific infrastructure requirements. Consequently, the cost estimates presented here should be interpreted as indicative rather than definitive.

It should also be noted that we model a pressure-stabilised single charge-discharge cycle. Future work should focus on coupling the storage models to realistic charging and discharging schedules derived from generation and demand profiles. The

Figure 2: Cavern gas and wall temperature evolution for ACAES and hydrogen storage systems in shallow and deep salt caverns.

present work has focused primarily on thermodynamic performance and capital cost. A natural extension is the development of a full techno-economic framework to enable the calculation of the levelised cost of storage (LCOS).

4 Conclusion

Overall, ACAES provides substantially higher round-trip efficiencies and lower total capital costs than hydrogen storage, achieving approximately 64% round-trip efficiency compared with 38–40% for hydrogen across both cavern depths. In contrast, hydrogen storage offers significantly greater energy density and lower capital cost per unit of stored energy, particularly at greater depths. The results therefore highlight a fundamental trade-off between energy efficiency and storage density, with cavern depth exerting a strong influence on both system performance and economics. ACAES appears better suited to shorter-duration energy shifting where round-trip efficiency is critical, whilst hydrogen storage is more attractive for long-duration and seasonal storage applications. Given the scale of future UK storage requirements, salt cavern resources may ultimately support a combination of both technologies, with the optimal choice dependent on the characteristics of local demand and generation patterns.

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